

IMMUNOMORPHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF BCL-2 MARKER EXPRESSION IN VARIOUS FORMS OF ADENOIDS IN CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

The sclerotic hypertrophic form of adenoids is predominantly observed in older children and adolescents suffering from chronic adenoiditis. In this condition, pronounced proliferation of connective tissue is noted at the base of the pharyngeal lymphoid tissue, beginning from the area adjacent to the palatine bone and extending toward the periosteum. The connective tissue bundles are characterized by low cellularity and a coarse fibrous structure and are distributed as thick strands extending from the basal layer of the adenoid tissue to its superficial layers.

Relevance of the problem

According to data from leading clinical centers worldwide, diseases of the lymphoid pharyngeal ring (Waldeyer's lymphadenoid ring) occupy a leading position among otorhinolaryngological pathologies in childhood. The proportion of children with chronic adenoid tonsillitis ranges from 20% to 50%, while among frequently ill children it reaches 37–70% (Makkaev H.M., 2002; Mishunin Yu.V. et al., 2003; Bikova V.P., Kalinin D.V., 2011; Nikolaeva A.I., 2011; Gouletal M., 2007).

The highest prevalence of lymphadenoid pharyngeal ring pathology is characteristic of children aged 3 to 7 years, regardless of place of residence. However, pathology of the pharyngeal tonsil occurs significantly more frequently (2.1-fold) in children living in areas with high levels of air pollution compared to those residing in environmentally favorable regions.

Under normal physiological conditions, the nasopharyngeal tonsil, similar to other tonsils of the Pirogov–Waldeyer ring, ensures the maintenance of immune homeostasis and the full induction of antigen-specific adaptive immune responses (Saidov M.Z. et al., 2011). The causes of pharyngeal tonsil hypertrophy include childhood infectious diseases (measles, whooping cough, scarlet fever, diphtheria, influenza, etc.), as well as acute and chronic inflammatory diseases of the upper respiratory tract. At the same time, constitutional characteristics of the child also play an important role. This is evidenced by cases where hypertrophy of the pharyngeal lymphoid apparatus develops in the absence of inflammation. Such conditions are regarded in pediatrics as manifestations of constitutional anomalies—namely lymphatic-hypoplastic diathesis—characterized by the development of *status thymicolymphaticus*, secondary immunodeficiency, and difficulties in treatment.

Materials and methods

Morphological and immunohistochemical examinations of nasopharyngeal tonsils were conducted in 64 children aged 1 to 10 years diagnosed with adenoid disease and treated at the ADTI Clinic and the private IMPULS Clinic during the period from 2020 to 2024. The study assessed age-related prevalence and pathomorphological features of adenoids using clinical-anamnestic, morphological, and statistical research methods.

Discussion and results

The Bcl-2 domain, located on human chromosome 18, consists of 16 proteins with anti-apoptotic properties. Among them, the Bcl-2 protein is a homologous protein that slows down apoptotic processes. This protein has a molecular weight of approximately 22 kDa and is localized in the cell and nuclear membranes, sarcoplasm, and mitochondrial membranes. High positive expression of this protein inhibits calcium ion release, suppresses lipid peroxidation, reduces antioxidant activity, and decreases nitric oxide synthase activity.

The primary function of Bcl-2 is to prevent the release of mitochondrial pro-apoptotic molecules such as cytochrome C, AIF, and ATP through membrane pores. By binding to the mitochondrial membrane and closing these pores, Bcl-2 interrupts pro-apoptotic signaling pathways, thereby preventing the development of apoptosis.

Immunohistochemical examination of the sclerotic hypertrophic form of adenoids revealed pronounced sclerosis and fibrosis of adenoid tissue. Due to excessive proliferation of connective tissue structures, lymphoid cells within the adenoid tissue exhibit relative atrophy and reduced proliferative activity. As lymphoid cells are preserved mainly between connective tissue bundles, Bcl-2 marker expression in their cytoplasm was observed at varying levels.

Within sclerotic bundles, connective tissue cells—primarily fibroblasts—predominate, and Bcl-2 expression is virtually absent in these cells. However, low-level expression of the marker was detected in reticular stromal cells and lymphoid cells located between sclerotic bundles.

Polymorphometric analysis demonstrated that the average Bcl-2 expression level in the sclerotic hypertrophic form of adenoids was 32.4%.

Conclusion

Considering that the anti-apoptotic Bcl-2 protein is normally localized in the cell and nuclear membranes as well as in mitochondria, its expression was found to vary across different histotopographic forms of adenoid disease. Specifically, low expression was observed in the lymphoproliferative form, moderate expression in the interstitial proliferative-inflammatory form, high expression in the angiomatous form, and moderate expression in the sclerotic form.

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